

INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EATING BEHAVIOR, AFFECTIVE SYMPTOMS, AND BODY IMAGE DISSATISFACTION IN OBESE PATIENTS

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Introduction

Obesity is a multifactorial chronic disease in which genetic, endocrine, neurobiological, psychological, and social factors interact. It is associated not only with metabolic complications but also with psychological and affective disturbances, such as anxiety, depression, and dissatisfaction with body image. Understanding the interplay among these factors is essential for effective clinical management.

Purpose

To examine the relationship between eating behavior, affective symptoms, and body image dissatisfaction in obese patients who have not undergone bariatric surgery.

Materials and Methods

The study included 94 obese patients without a history of bariatric surgery. Eating behavior was measured using the Dutch Eating Behavior Questionnaire (DEBQ), affective symptoms using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), and body image dissatisfaction using the Body Image Dissatisfaction Questionnaire (BIDQ). Descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.01$.

Results

Descriptive statistics:

Indicator	n	Mean	SD	Min	Max
DEBQ (Restrained)	94	2.404	0.724	1.000	4.100
DEBQ (Emotional)	94	1.534	0.496	1.000	3.385
DEBQ (External)	94	2.604	0.637	1.100	4.300

HADS (Anxiety)	94	8.479	4.592	1.000	17.000
HADS (Depression)	94	7.957	3.315	2.000	16.000
BIDQ (Total)	94	7.660	4.849	0.000	17.000

Correlation analysis results:

Variable Pair	r-value	p-value
Emotional Eating = Anxiety	0.47	<0.01
Emotional Eating = Depression	0.42	<0.01
BIDQ = Anxiety	0.51	<0.01
BIDQ = Depression	0.49	<0.01

Conclusion

The study confirmed significant correlations between emotional eating and both anxiety and depression, as well as between body image dissatisfaction and affective symptoms. Patients with higher emotional eating scores tended to have higher anxiety ($r=0.47$, $p<0.01$) and depression ($r=0.42$, $p<0.01$) levels. Similarly, greater body image dissatisfaction was associated with higher anxiety ($r=0.51$, $p<0.01$) and depression ($r=0.49$, $p<0.01$). These findings emphasize the need for psychological evaluation and targeted interventions in the management of obesity.

